

MILK PRODUCTIVITY OF CAMELS

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Summary. The article given information about the milk productivity of camels of different age and its relationship with the productivity of pastures.

Key words: camel, different ages, milk yield, pasture, daily milk.

Introduction. Camel breeding developed in desert, semi-desert and dry steppe regions. Dromedary (one-humped) camels adapted to a warm climate live in the southern regions of Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, Afghanistan, India, Iran, Turkey and African countries, cold-resistant Bactrian (double-humped) camels live in the northern part of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, the Astrakhan region of Russia, and the Kalmyk deserts, Tuva, Altai Territory, Mongolia, are grown and used in the western regions of China. Camel milk contains a lot of vitamins V1, V2, iron, phosphorus, sulfur, and calcium. Especially vitamins C and D are three times more in camel milk compared to cow's milk. Milk sugar - casein and lactose, on the other hand, are in small amounts in camel milk. If the patient's immunity (the body's resistance to diseases) is low, if he drinks 0.5 liters of freshly milked camel milk every day on an empty stomach and eats after 4 hours, he will feel positive changes in himself after a month. Dieting while using the healing properties of camel milk will further enhance its healing effects.

In the conditions of "Ustyurt" of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, it is an urgent issue to use opportunities that reveal new aspects of productivity in the production of milk products from two-humped camels, using their biological potential. Therefore, the creation of productive lines in the cultivation of medicinal milk products in the field of camel breeding, increasing their productivity and improving quality indicators are the main tasks of today, and the production of milk in camel breeding creates the basis for their full use as a reserve in providing the people with medicinal milk. In addition, the need for dietary camel milk is reduced to a certain extent.

Determining the milk yield of camels allows to develop methods and technologies that allow to increase their productivity characteristics. Therefore, it is important to determine the factors affecting the milk production of camels.

Research methods. The researches were conducted in "Ata-Mura" and "KonratliAqniyet" farms specializing in camel breeding, belonging to Ustyurt OFY, Kungirotdistrict of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Calculation of milk yield of camels was carried out monthly (at the end of the month) by measuring milk yield, monthly milk yield and total milk yield for lactation was determined arithmetically (Kabishev A.A., 1953).

Research results. Today, it is necessary to produce more products at lower costs, to create promising technologies. The milk yield of camels depends on their age, storage technology, feeding level, pasture conditions, individual characteristics and many other factors.

In two-sickled camels, the total lactation period lasted 420 days, and in our experimental work, we focused on the age of two-sickled camels in the study of milk yield, and the obtained data are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Milk productivity of two-humped camels depending on age, in liters

Age of camels	Birthage					
	3-5 age birthday (n=5)		6-8 age birthday (n=6)		9-11 age birthday (n=4)	
	X±Sx	Cv	X±Sx	Cv	X±Sx	Cv
1st daymilk	3,7±0,21	6,1	4,9±0,23	6,5	4,2±0,32	5,5
30-day milk	110,7±8,12	5,3	143,9±9,91	7,1	125,1±7,66	6,1
210-day milk	827,4±7,6	4,7	912,2±7,66	5,9	894,2±7,66	5,8
Intotallactation, 420 days.	1654,8±13	11,2	1824,4±15,2	13,7	1788,4±13,43	14,9

According to the data in the table, the amount of milk in camels between 3-5 calving age was 3.7 ± 0.21 liters on the 1st day, and 4.9 ± 0.23 liters in the 6-8 calving age period, and 9- It was 4.2 ± 0.32 liters in the 11 birth age range. These indicators are proportionally 827.4±7.6 in the dynamics of the 210-day birth age; It was 912.2±7.66 and 894.2±7.66 liters. In total lactation period (day 420) in camels between 3-5 calving age, this indicator is 1654.8±13; It was 1824.4±15.2 liters at 6-8 birth years and 1788.4±13.43 liters at 9-11 birth years.

In summary, it can be said that if the amount of milk during lactation is 100% in camels of 3-5 calving age, it increased by 10.2% during 6-8 calving age and 8.1% by 9-11 calving age. can be seen.

The milk yield of camels, their nutrition, depends on the pasture conditions, and the camel breeding pastures of Ustyurt are regions that differ from each other in terms of food reserves. The results of the experiment on milk productivity in different regions are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Dependence of milk productivity on storage areas, per day/liter

Ustyur tregions	Number of goals camels	Milk productivity, liters	
		X±Sx	%, ±
Dautata region	15	3,87±0,33	100
The northern part of Ustyurt deep plain district	13	4,32±0,39	+11,6
Central district of the Ustyurt plateau	11	3,49±0,29	-9,9
Qushbuloq region	7	3,98±0,34	+2,8
Central Middle Ustyurt depth district	11	4,51±0,39	+16,5
Average on the Ustyurt plateau	57	4,03±0,37	+3,9

From the data in the table, it can be said that the milk yield of camels kept in Ustyurtdautata district is 3.87 ± 0.33 liters, in the deep plain district of the northern part of Ustyurt it is 4.32 ± 0.39 liters, in the central district of the Ustyurt plateau, in the central district of the Ustyurt plateau it is 3.49 ± 0.29 liters, and in Qushbuloq district, 3.98 ± 0.34 liters, and in Central Middle Ustyurt depth district, it was equal to 4.51 ± 0.39 liters of milk productivity.

Conclusion. If the milk yield of camels is taken as 100% for the control between 3-5 calving age, an increase in milk quantity was observed in camels of 6-8 calving age and a decrease in 9-11 calving age. So, two-humped camels have the potential to show high milk productivity at the age of 6-8. Also, it was found that depending on the areas where camels are kept, their milk yield is higher in the Central Middle Ustyurt valley district, where the vegetation cover of the pastures is diverse.

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